

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF STUDYING TRADITIONAL NAMES IN LINGUISTICS

Zilola Pazilova

Teacher, Fergana State University

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Abstract

In this article, the history of the formation of ethnolinguistics in Uzbek and German languages, the work carried out in this regard, the traditions that are part of ethnolinguistics and their role in society are analyzed in detail.

Key words: ethnolinguistics, traditions, national value, history, tradition, spiritual heritage, cultural wealth, historical monuments, ethnoculture.

The concept of nation is considered one of the most relevant aspects as humanity is formed in its civilization over centuries and reflects its unique characteristics in the social community. All peoples of the world have their own ethnocultural characteristics. Nations and peoples are distinguished in the world due to ethno-cultural characteristics, and peoples try to show their qualities in mutual relations. With this, they try to show the superiority and advantage of their culture and try to prove that they belong to the main links of the world civilization in terms of culture. These features are made up of various components of the social sign, which is recognized in relation to the general culture of the nation or people, as it is formed in its own way in each person. One such component is customs.

Traditions are the best, instructive lessons of human life, his life and social activity, work, exemplary life from ancient times. We will not be mistaken if we say that they are lessons of guidance for the descendants and ancestors.

The main criteria that form national values are the nation's history, customs, traditions, life values, as well as its spiritual heritage, cultural assets, and old historical monuments. In the dictionary of philosophy, «Tradition is a procedure accepted by the whole nation as traditions; It is defined as «pictures, principles». Traditions cover all spheres of social life and find their expression in them. The customs of a certain people are considered a component of the ethno-culture of this people. Any ethnoculture finds its expression in the language of this people.

All peoples living on earth are distinguished by their language, origin, material and spiritual culture, and household lifestyle.

Recently, a separate field of linguistics, which studies the linguistic tools representing the ethno-culture of the people, has also emerged, and this field has become known as ethnolinguistics. Today, ethnolinguistics is a branch of science that studies the ethnoculture of a certain people with the help of linguistic methods.

Ethnolinguistics as a purely linguistic direction emerged in the first quarter of the 20th century. F.Boas is recognized as its founder. One of the main tasks of ethnolinguistics founded by F.Boas was to determine the issue of genetic kinship of Indian tribes.

In the process of studying the influence of ethnoculture, special importance was attached to ethnic traditions and their names.

For this reason, the presence of a common name and a common language, customs and traditions of each ethnic group were recognized as important features that distinguish them from other ethnic groups. It seems that traditions are recognized as a component of ethnic ethnoculture as the main factor determining its existence, and the study of its names is considered an important direction of ethnolinguistics.

German linguist Anke Fischer interprets the origin of customs as follows: «In our region, pagan traditions from Germanic times can still be felt. Here flourished a famous rich belief that tried to interpret the incomprehensible forces of nature. The mixture of ancient Germanic paganism's belief in Greco-Roman gods, mythical creatures, and evil spirits shaped many of the acts we see in rituals today, but whose origins can no longer be explained. However, the greatest influence on Western culture came from Christianity, and many of the holidays we celebrate today have been based on it for centuries.»

German linguist Helga Maria Wolff, in her study *Die schönsten Bräuche & Rituale und Traditionen* (The Most Beautiful Customs & Rituals and Paintings), opens a window into the past in this fascinating and fascinating study that has long been celebrated customs, rituals and traditions that accompany people throughout the year, where they come from and how they came about are researched. The significance of the study is that customs such as Christmas or Easter, weddings or funerals, May Festival, Eve, Baptism, are still held in many places and are celebrated in various forms. details are given about the bride and the fact that many of them have been forgotten.

Indeed, the traditions of each nation can change over time and be updated in accordance with the times.

In the study of German linguist Anke Fischer entitled «Feste und Bräuche in Deutschland» (German holidays and traditions), every region celebrates from large holidays such as Easter or Christmas to small ones, which are celebrated in the family, community, circle of friends or in the heart of nature. it refers to the customs that take place in the circle and with the closest relatives, which are the sum of all the rituals, such as birth, marriage, and mourning. In addition, the study shows that traditions determine people's lives and behavior, as well as the sequence of fasting, penance and holidays, forty holidays celebrated throughout the year in most major regions and even in Central Europe and their origins. will be explained in detail.

We can see that a lot of German scientists tackled this topic.

German linguist Angelica Feilhauer's study *Feste feiern in Deutschland* (Celebration of Holidays in Germany) is a travel guide to customs past and present, including past and present customs, old traditions or the origins of customs and festivals associated with historical events, their constant change and the various manifestations of tradition. In his opinion, in most cases it is impossible to fully determine the origin of holidays. They often appeared in close connection with the course of nature throughout the year, marked seasonal turning points, or appeared in connection with certain life situations or important events in the past. They have moved from one culture to another and have been interpreted differently over time. Especially in the 19th century, during the reformation and enlightenment, i.e., the conversion of church or monastery property into state property, many traditions and holidays were revived.

Recent research shows that these customs, which persisted after World War II, are not so old or historical. Through Angelica Failhauer's research, it is possible to learn about individual holidays celebrated throughout the year and the traditions associated with them, dating back hundreds of years or more recently.

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